

ISic1391

Greek inscription recording enjoyment of a spring

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

touristic text

Material

natural rock

Object

rock face

Editor

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Autopsy

2015.07.03

Last Change

2020-06-16 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based upon autopsy, in line with edition prepared for Adrano museum catalogue

Place of origin (ancient)

Adranon

Place of origin (modern)

Adrano

Provenance

In situ on the natural rock at Fonte delle Favare, contrada Polichello, 3.5 km NW of the centre of Adrano

Coordinates

37.680917, 14.801028

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Adrano, in situ

Physical Description

The inscription is engraved on the vertical face of the natural rock, part of a low cliff immediately above a natural spring, on a terrace above the river Simeto. The text is preserved complete. The height of the inscribed area is 0.29-0.34m; the width of the inscribed area 1.25m.

Dimensions

Height 29-34 cm

Width 125 cm

Depth NA cm

Layout

The text maintains a clear left margin, laid out over three lines. The extended spacing in lines 1 and 2 has sometimes suggested to editors that the text divides into columns; however this is probably to compensate for the fact that lines 2 and 3 are shortened by the insertion of a large engraved palm leaf (20 cm high) on the right margin.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The text is engraved in large bold letters, with the topmost stroke often extended vertically above the letter on A, Λ, Δ. Letter forms are somewhat variable within the inscription, with lunate and straight sigma used indiscriminately; epsilon is normally straight, but appears lunate in ΦΗΕΙΝΟC in line 2; alpha is normally straight but displays broken bar in ΕΥΦΡΑΝΘΗΣΑΝ in line 3; phi has an angular eye in lines 1 and 2 but a rounded eye in line 3; variation within texts is however common, and it is not necessary to assume that this reflects different hands in use within the text. Ligatures are employed several times in the text, which has been the source of several confused readings in the past.

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 70-90 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Κελαδιάνος, Λάλος, Ῥοῦφος
2. Φησεῖνος, Εὐσέβης
3. Παυλεῖνος εὐφράνθησαν

Apparatus

Text based upon autopsy

Translation (en)

Keladianos, Lalos, Roupfos, Pheseinos, Eusebes, Pauleinos enjoyed themselves

Commentary

The inscription was first recorded by Gualtherus (1624, p. 50 nr. 333) and has been repeated many times since. The text was improved almost completely (by conjecture) by Franz in CIG III, 5741, but the edition by Kaibel in IG XIV, 572 was a retrograde step. The text was improved, through autopsy on 2 April 1898, by Paolo Orsi (1900, p. 44 nr. 3, cf. P. Orsi and P. Pelagatti, *Adrano e la città sicula del Mendolito 1898-1909*, in *Archivio Storico Siracusano*, 13 14, 1967 1968p. 151), but the first wholly accurate text, albeit with an artificial division into two columns, was that of Manganaro (1961, p. 132; better edition in Manganaro 1992, p. 497-500 nr. 8; cf. Ferrua 1989, nr. 472 who followed the unsatisfactory edition of Soraci 1958, p. 257). A number of writers and scholars, beginning with Pirro 1733 [1644] have in the past taken the text to be non-Greek, due to the difficulty of transcribing and reconciling the ligatures and the non-standard forms of some of the names (definitive rejection by Schmoll 1958, p. 39 nr. 40). The final verb, εὐφραίνω, was correctly transcribed and translated by Orsi (guessed already in CIG III, 5741). As Manganaro observed, it is a common word in the context of banquets, and should be understood to reflect the enjoyment of the spring (Manganaro 1992, p. 500 n. 87 after Robert (*Hellenica* X, 1955, p. 199 n. 7); see more recently, e.g., BE 1992.154 and 1997.127-128 for examples of ancient glassware); the innuendo suggested by Libertini 1932, p. 13-14 is unnecessary.

It is difficult to date any inscription on the basis of its letter forms alone, and especially a rupestral one of this sort. The inscription undoubtedly belongs to the second century AD or later (Manganaro 1961, p. 133 suggested the third or early fourth century, in part on the style of the palm; he revised this (1992, p. 497) to the second century, apparently on the basis of the letter forms; others have simply suggested the Christian era). The use of single names, three of Greek type and three Roman could reflect servile status (Manganaro 1992, p.

500), but need not do so given the informal context.

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